

SENTINEL-HUB cloud based platform utilization, for COPERNICUS Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2, as well as VHR data processing

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Abstract: This report is focused on the utilization of cloud based platform – SENTINEL-HUB©, operated by Sinergise© Slovenia, for processing of a large amount of satellite data from different sensors. The aim is to demonstrate the processing of ESA's COPERNICUS Sentinel-1 time series SAR, and reference optical Sentinel-2 imagery, in the purpose of SRTI-BAS/ESA's project - "FoReS". Also, the report describes the processing of optical VHR satellite imagery from the WorldView and GeoEye missions, via the SENTINEL-HUB platform. The test site is located in mountainous forest in Stara Planina mountain massif. Firstly, an overview of the platform and its activation through dedicated API key was made. The user interface, making cURL requests, and formulating various functions in Javascript are covered. The processing of individual radar images from Sentinel-1 and optical images from Sentinel-2 is demonstrated. Averaging SAR time series were then performed for two summer periods, in the years 2020 and 2021, in the purpose of FoReS – WP4. Two SAR indices were also calculated - dual-pol Radar Vegetation Index (dRVI) and Degree of Polarization (DoP), available at the Sentinel-Hub's Custom Repository. Also, for the FoReS - WP4 purposes, high-resolution imagery from the MAXAR's collection of WorldView and GeoEye were provided. Four-band composites, pansharpen image, and the Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI) were calculated. In conclusion, the author brings the focus on the convenience of working with the cloud based platform SENTINEL-HUB with dedicated APIs, highlighting its advantages in processing a large set of data. Access to the platform, as well as the VHR data, was carried out through a project proposal to the ESA, via Notation of Request (NoR).

Обработка на сателитни данни по програма КОПЕРНИК - Sentinel-1 и Sentinel-2, и такива с висока ПРС, чрез облачна платформа SENTINEL-HUB

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Резюме: Това изследване е фокусирано върху използването на високо технологичната облачна платформа на Словенската компания Sinergise – SENTINEL HUB©, за обработка на сателитни данни с висока пространствена разделителна способност (ПРС). Целта на изследването е да демонстрира обработката на радарни времеви серии и оптични референтни изображения, от радарната и оптична мисия по програма КОПЕРНИК на Европейската Космическа Агенция (ЕКА) – Sentinel-1 и Sentinel-2, по линия на проект към ЕКА – „FoReS“. Също така, в доклада е описана и обработката на оптични сателитни данни с висока ПРС (VHR) от мисии WorldView и GeoEye. Тестовия участък е в Стара Планина, в района на УОГС „Петрохан“. Първо е направен обзор на платформата и активирането ѝ чрез генерирания API key. Разгледан е потребителския интерфейс, извършването на cURL – заявки и формулирането на различни функции в Javascript. Демонстрирана е обработката на отделни радарни изображения от Sentinel-1 и оптични от Sentinel-2. След това е извършено пресмятане на средни стойности на радарни времеви серии за два летни периода, през 2020-та и 2021-ва години, за целите на „FoReS“, работен пакет (ПП) 4. Извършено е и пресмятане на два радарни индекса – dual-pol Radar Vegetation Index (dRVI) и Degree of Polarization (DoP). За целите на „FoReS“ - РП4 е предоставен същият достъп до изображения с висока ПРС от колекция MAXAR, от WorldView и GeoEye. Пресметнати са четириканални композити и Нормализирания индекс на растителността (NDVI). В заключение, авторът показва удобството за работа с облачната платформа, като изтъква нейните предимства

при обработката на голям набор от данни. Достъпът до платформата и данните с висока ПРС е осъществен чрез изготвено проектно предложение към ЕКА, през Nottation of Request (NoR). Изследването е представено пред Институтски семинар на ИКИТ-БАН.

Introduction

Interest in studying forests ecosystems with Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) has a long history in the remote sensing, including variety of SAR based methods and data (Cloude & Pottier, 1996; Balzter, et al., 2007; Santoro, et al., 2015; Santoro, et al., 2021). Reasons to choose SAR to study natural media is that it overcomes some limitations, which the classical optical approach have (Fernandez-Ordonez, et al., 2009). Despite of that, the physical coherent nature of SAR induces additional frustration during interpretation. That is a kind of characteristic noise, but in essence holds the structure of the distributed scatterers. It is called “speckle” and could be suppressed by variety of coherent and incoherent approaches to improve the quality of the SAR imagery (Ferro-Famil, 2006). Besides, measuring the polarization states of the registered SAR image, could be in dual- or full-polarimetry that changes sensitivity of the method (Erxue, et al., 2009). Polarimetric analysis and POLinSAR is of great importance to retrieve the geometric properties, and the vertical forest structure (Yamaguchi, et al., 2010; López-Martínez, et al., 2005a; Papathanassiou & Cloude, 2001).

The dual polarization SAR instruments, such as European Space Agency (ESA) COPERNICUS program - Sentinel-1 SAR mission, can achieve accurate delineation of the land cover classes (Banqué, et al., 2015). The SAR vegetation indices derived from the Sentinel-1 SAR data, such as the dual-pol Radar Vegetation Index (dRVI), shows promising sensitivity to the vegetation structure and correlates with the optical NDVI (Mandal, et al., 2020). Although assessing forest structure via SAR signal is achievable task, it could be limited due to saturation problems at the backscatter intensities (Imhoff, 1993). Also, environmental conditions in mountainous forests such as seasonality is of great importance for forest studies (Thiel & Schullius, 2013). The SAR time series analysis is a promising approach that could overcome in some degree saturation, environmental and stochastic factors (Santoro, et al., 2011). Time series analysis based solely on SAR intensities is promising to assess forest structure where to successfully delineate the forest types (Quegan, et al., 2017). In that relation, the ESA Copernicus - Sentinel-1 dual-pol C-band SAR mission offers great perspectives in the forest domain studies and is used in AGB estimation ESA’s projects (Quegan, et al., 2017; Santoro, et al., 2019).

Assessing needs for remote sensing studies of large-scale mountainous forests brings the SAR time series analysis as a very important approach with positive outcomes for the scientific community. The implementation of large amounts of satellite data is considered problematic due to manual execution of a complex workflow within standalone desktop software. The methodological approach always considers access to data, where to be implemented must be priorly downloaded physically on the local storage. This slows down the overall processing and imposes requirements for the hardware and mostly the availability of computational capacity. Solution of this could be cloud based analysis with direct access to the desired satellite dataset. Such a solutions are already offered by the Google Earth Engine© and the cloud-based platform – SENTINEL-HUB©. The SENTINEL-HUB is an extensive engine accessible via internet, which provides vast processing of large amount of satellite data (Sinergise, 2023a). It serves as an “all-in-one” platform. This is especially vital for methodological approaches based on the time series analysis having execution of a complex workflow, which may include SAR and optical data processing from different vendors. In those cases, such a platform could utterly diminish processing via desktop software and shorten the computation time. The SENTINEL-HUB provides direct access to the ESA COPERNICUS Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 optical missions.

This report aims representation of the utilization of SENTINEL-HUB for fast processing of Sentinel-1 SAR time series, as well as optical data from Sentinel-2 and VHR data from WorldView, and GeoEye, provided from MAXAR. This processing is in purpose of ESA’s project “FoReS”, held in Space Research and Technology Institute at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences – SRTI-BAS, and the work package – WP4. Firstly, the sample processing is shown with Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 imagery. Afterwards the processing of Sentinel-1 SAR time series is reported with estimation of statistical mean and computation of SAR based indices. Finally, VHR data processing from the MAXAR’s collection is reported. This report is proceeding of the conference – “COPE4BG”, held online in December 2022.

Data and test site

Two types of satellite data in terms of accessibility and spatial resolution are used. The first group is the freely available ESA COPERNICUS satellite imagery that constitutes of Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 optical data. Regarding Sentinel-1 the Ground Range Detected (GRD) data products are

assessed. Regarding Sentinel-2 the L2A data products are assessed. In the second group, the Very High Resolution (VHR) optical data from WorldView and GeoEye satellite data is used, as part from the “MAXAR” collection provided by SENTINEL-HUB. The spatial resolution varies from 0.5 for Panchromatic to 2 m for multispectral images. Access to the VHR data from MAXAR and to the SENTINEL-HUB platform is provided by ESA, via approved application at “Nottation of Request” (i.e. NoR). Provided access to the platform was for one year with “Basic plan”, which allows 70K processing units per a month, 500 per minute, as well as 70K requests per month and 500 per minute. The allowed quota for the VHR data from MAXAR’s collection was designated to a value of 28 km².

Different locations whole over the country of Bulgaria are used to test processing via SENTINEL-HUB platform. The general test locations are mountainous test sites in Vitosha Mountain and Stara Planina Mountain. But also, Rhodope Mountain, along the Test Educational Forest Entity (TEFR) of Petrohan, the western heights around Sofia, and the land areas with cities of Sofia and Burgas.

Methodology

Main methodology consists of utilization of the SENTINEL-HUB platform for SAR and optical data processing. Because different satellite data products are utilized methodology is separated into three sub sections.

The first one is dedicated to optical processing of Sentinel-2 (S2) satellite images, where L2A data products are processed to output RGB composites from different S2 band combinations.

The second one is dedicated to the SAR data processing of Sentinel-1 (S1), where GRD data products are processed. This methodological subsection is based on the normalized backscatter of Gamma-Nought, and calculation of the SAR indices of dRVI and Degree of Polarization (DoP), as a time series of data. It also includes the statistical mean estimation from the SAR time series for the span of three months in the summer of 2020 (June-August), and for the winter of 2020 and 2021 (January-March). The methodological approach includes the following SAR processing: calibration to Gamma-Nought, terrain normalization and terrain flattening (Small, et al., 2010), incoherent speckle filtering with algorithm of Refined Lee (Yommy, et al., 2015), and window of 5x5 pixels, and final SAR geocoding with Range-Doppler approach by using a reference DEM (Bhanumurthy & Mallikarjuna, 2011).

The third one is optical VHR data processing from WorldView and GeoEye from MAXAR collection, where three different output products were generated: pansharpened four-band composite, with highest available spatial resolution, an NDVI RGB reference raster and floating-point raster, and a three-band composite with lower spatial resolution.

The SENTINEL-HUB platform implements five major Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that allow access to different features and functionalities, to programmatically process satellite data regarding the user needs (Sinergise, 2023b). Those which are assessed in this study are: *Processing API*, *Statistical API*, *Catalog API* and *Third-Party Data Import API*. In addition, must be stated that the standards and protocols from the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) are integrated in the platform, where produced spatial outputs could be easily distributed to desktop applications via standard WMS, WCS, WMTS and WFS services, or RESTful APIs (Sinergise, 2023b).

Scripts

Functionalities in the SENTINEL-HUB platform are accessed via user defined scripts, where JavaScript is used for functions, and structured JSON is used to assign parameters to the output cURL request. The developing of user defined scripts is facilitated by the Custom Processing Scripts repository available for the users of SENTINEL-HUB (Sinergise, 2022). The initial scripts for testing representation of the SAR and optical data are based on sample scripts found in the repository, in sections dedicated for Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 (Sinergise, 2022). For Sentinel-2 RGB composites the sample scripts representations are used. The Sentinel-1 time series means estimates are calculated via developed functions from the author in JavaScript, based on sample script from the repo. The calculations comprise the backscatter Sigma-Nought, as well as the dRVI and DoP. For the calculation of dRVI and DoP, the sample script for “RVI4S1” is used available in the repo (Mandal, 2021). Various tutorials and the available API reference is used during the script’s development from the author (Sinergise, 2022a). Considering the processing of the VHR data from MAXAR’s collection, limited information was found at the repo. Therefore, a variety of experiments were done with the data to develop the final version of the functions in JavaScript, to calculate the pansharpened composite with the NDVI and the multispectral.

Initial set-up

An initial set-up of the SENTINEL-HUB platform is performed where the API key is issued, which is needed to be implemented in the cURL requests. It is done by following steps from the available webinars in the Sinergise’s channel in YouTube© (Sinergise, 2021). Some tests for firing HTTP requests

to the Processing API was performed by using the Postman API OS platform, where HTTP headers set was tested (Postman Inc., 2022). The user interface of the SENTINEL-HUB is named - "Request Builder", which constitutes of several panels. The main ones are the function panel and the JSON panel with the body of the cURL request. Some default setup is applied in the first login into the portal.

An initial set-up of the SENTINEL-HUB's user interface (Request Builder) was done. It includes the set of the coordinated reference system (CRS), where the Pseudo Mercator with EPSG code of 3857 was applied. Also, for testing purposes two additional CRS were also used with the EPSG codes of 4326 (geographical coordinates) and 32634 (Universal Transverse Mercator in Zone of 34).

The output spatial resolution for the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data products was set to 10 m. The output raster format was set to GeoTIFF (Fig. 1). The acceptable area of interest (AOI) was found to be maximum of 100 km², where any larger AOI led to the Processing API's crashing, which stops execution. For the reference DEM, the available "Copernicus DEM" with spatial resolution of 30 m was set.

Fig. 1. The Request Builder which is the main user interface of the SENTINEL-HUB platform

Results and Discussion

Processing API

The first results showed simplicity in the initial setup, ease of use with the user interface of the Request Builder, and very fast and convenient processing via the Processing API. The dedicated to the Sentinel-1 and 2 JavaScript functions at the repo were modified, where to produce the normalized backscatter in different polarizations, polarization ratio, calculation of dRVI for S1, for the cities of Sofia and Burgas, and RGB composite for S2, for the city of Burgas (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The first results of processing via Processing API, where: A) S2 NIR-SWIR-RED, of Burgas; B) S1 dRVI, of Sofia, Winter 2021. Note: used CRS is EPSG:3857; date of acquisition for A) is 23-05-2020, for B) 07-02-2021.

In this approach the output results are directly shown on the screen within the user interface of the Request Builder, as RGB representations, which can easily be downloaded after execution.

The second test with S2 RGB composites was done at the test site at TEFR of Petrohan. Two reference periods were assessed for the desired change detection, with dates of acquisition 27-06-2020 and 22-06-2022 (Fig.3). Two RGB composites were successfully produced by means of S2 bands: *NIR-SWIR-RedEdge* (B08/B11/B04), and “Natural Colors” representation (B04/B03/B02) (Sinergise, 2022b).

The third test included time series processing of the S1 GRD data products, for time span of three months from June and August in 2020, and from January to March in 2021. The reason is to study the impact of seasonality in SAR time series for different polarizations and SAR indices. The estimated statistical mean for the backscatter in both polarizations (VH and VV), as well as the dRVI and DoP, which included whole acquisitions at test site TEFR of Petrohan, showed high degree of filtering out the environmental factors (e.g. changes of dielectric constant due to wetness), and characteristic nose (i.e. speckle) (Fig. 4). The calculation was executed for a maximum duration of 3 minutes.

Fig. 3. The RGB composites resulted from S2 L2A products from 27-06-2020, near test site TEFR of Petrohan in Stara Planina, where: A) the NIR/SWIR/Red Edge (B08/B11/B04); B) Natural Colors (B04/B03/B02)

Fig. 4. The mean estimates from the summer SAR time series of 2020 (June-August), at TEFR of Petrohan, where: A) VV, B) VH, C) dRVI.

Results also confirmed that the geometric distortions strongly influence the mean estimates from the time series, whereas the winter estimates are more influenced by geometric distortions rather than the summer estimates. Also, interestingly the depolarization that exhibits the coniferous forest (the white patches at the dRVI, Fig.4-C) is much lower in wintertime rather than in summertime, therefore on the mean from winter SAR time series the differences between both polarizations diminish (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Comparison of mean estimates from different seasons, where: A) from summer SAR time series, B) from winter SAR time series. Note: in winter the intensities difference for both polarizations is close to zero, and differences in between diminish, thus the coniferous forest could not be determined (red circle and arrow).

The ease of use allows fast to designation of the desired orbit direction. In such manner both DESCENDING and ASCENDING orbit of SAR time series was calculated, with the rest of the processing parameters. Functionality in the Request Builder allows to store processing cURL with the concurrent JavaScript / JSON scripts, which facilitates processing in terms of different geographical scope.

Statistical API

To test this API, three different land cover types were delineated with a polygon in GIS, where: coniferous forest, broadleaf forest, grassland. The sample available script in the repo was further developed in Python, for the time span from November 2020 to April 2021. The result showed the time evolution of the backscatter and dRVI in those three samples, including the standard deviation (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Time evolution of the Gamma-Nought (backscatter coefficient) for dRVI, for three different land cover classes – coniferous forest, broadleaf forest, grassland, at test site TEFR of Petrohan

Third-Party Data Import (TPDI) API

In the purpose of WP4 from the “FoReS” ESA/SRTI-BAS project, five images from WorldView-2/3 and GeoEye-1 were utilized, for the post fire regrowth estimation in Biosphere Reserve in Vitosha Mountain, and area in Rhodope Mountain (Avetisyan, et al., 2023). Available scenes were selected and ordered according to the available quota and applied criteria for cloud cover and sunlight. After delivery the data was imported into the Request Builder via the TPDI API and processed via the Processing API. According to the methodology, the outputs are constituted as follows: Pansharp (RED, RED-Edge, NIR, SWIR) with pixel size of 0.5 m, Multispectral (RED, RED-Edge, NIR), NDVI, last two with pixel size of 2 m, and NDVI RGB, with pixel size of 2 m. Only the last product is provided as a PNG, despite that the rest are as floating point GeoTIFF (Fig. 7). Those products were also used as a validation into the WP4.

Fig. 7. The NDVI PNG and Multispectral (RED, RED-Edge, NIR) floating point RGB composite, from WorldView-2, in test area of “Bistrishko Branishte” Biosphere Reserve in Vitosha Mountain.

Conclusions

To conclude the analysis held in that study, it can be categorically confirmed that the cloud-based platform SENTINEL-HUB is valuable in remote sensing analysis with high load of data. The platform has higher utilization value in the SAR time series analysis with fast ability of processing and calculation of statistical mean. The user interface of the Request Builder is very intuitive and provides an “all-in-one” tool for remote sensing data processing. The availability of the “Custom Scripts” repository is of great importance for the user to have a ground base for script development, especially for the ESA COPERNICUS Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite data, but also for the closed access VHR optical data from the MAXAR collection.

Access to the platform and the VHR optical data from MAXAR collection, and the calculation of statistical mean for two summer periods from Sentinel-1 SAR time series, was of great importance for the tasks in WP4 of the ESA/SRTI-BAS “FoReS” project. The platform saved a lot of hours for processing a large amount of satellite data manually. It is great that for the scientific community the SENTINEL-HUB is provided ease of access through the possibility of the ESA’s “Nottation of Request”.

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References:

- Avetisyan, D., Stankova, N. & Dimitrov, Z., 2023. Assessment of Spectral Vegetation Indices Performance for Post-Fire Monitoring of Different Forest Environments. *MDPI*, 6(8), p. 290.
- Balster, H., Rowland, C. & Saich, P., 2007. Forest canopy height and carbon estimation at Monks Wood National Nature Reserve, UK, using dual-wavelength SAR interferometry. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, Volume 108, p. 224–239.
- Banqué, X. et al., 2015. *POLARIMETRY-BASED LAND COVER CLASSIFICATION WITH SENTINEL-1 DATA*, ESA.
- Bhanumurthy, Y. & Mallikarjuna, R. Y., 2011. SAR Data Processing with Range Cell Migration. *International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, 3(1), pp. 388–398.
- Cloude, S. R. & Pottier, E., 1996. A Review of Target Decomposition Theorems in Radar Polarimetry. *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON GEOSCIENCE AND REMOTE SENSING*, 34(2), p. 21.
- Erxue, C., Zengyuan, L., Xin, T. & Fengyun, F., 2009. *FOREST STRUCTURE INFORMATION EXTRACTION FROM POLARIMETRIC ALOS PALSAR DATA*. Beijing, Institute of Forest Resources Information Technique, Chinese Academy of Forestry.
- Fernandez-Ordóñez, Y., Soria-Ruiz, J. & Leblon, B., 2009. Forest Inventory using Optical and Radar Remote Sensing. *Advances in Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, pp. 540–556.
- Ferro-Famil, L., 2006. Speckle Filtering. In: *TUTORIAL ON SAR POLARIMETRY*. Rennes: ESA, p. 12.
- Imhoff, M. L., 1993. *Radar Backscatter/Biomass Saturation: Observations and Implications for Global Biomass Assessment*. Tokyo, s.n., p. 43–45.
- López-Martínez, C., Ferro-Famil, L. & Pottier, E., 2005a. *POLARIMETRIC DECOMPOSITIONS (PolSARPro)*, Rennes.
- Mandal, D., 2021. *Radar Vegetation Index for Sentinel-1 SAR data - RVI4S1 Script*. [Online] Available at: https://custom-scripts.sentinel-hub.com/sentinel-1/radar_vegetation_index/
- Mandal, D. et al., 2020. Dual polarimetric radar vegetation index for crop growth monitoring using sentinel-1 SAR data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, Volume 247, p. 17.
- Papathanassiou, K. P. & Cloude, S. R., 2001. Single-Baseline Polarimetric SAR Interferometry. *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON GEOSCIENCE AND REMOTE SENSING*, 39(11), pp. 2352–2364.
- Postman Inc., 2022. *Postman APIs*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.postman.com/>
- Quegan, S. et al., 2017. *D6 – Global Biomass Map: Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document*, Frascati: ESA-ESRIN.

- Santoro, M. et al., 2015. Forest growing stock volume of the northern hemisphere: Spatially explicit estimates for 2010 derived from Envisat ASAR. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, Volume 168, p. 316–334.
- Santoro, M. et al., 2011. Retrieval of growing stock volume in boreal forest using hyper-temporal series of Envisat ASAR ScanSAR backscatter measurements. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, Volume 115, p. 490–507.
- Santoro, M. et al., 2021. The global forest above-ground biomass pool for 2010 estimated from high-resolution satellite observations. *Earth System Science Data*, Volume 13, p. 3927–3950.
- Santoro, M., Quegan, S. & Seifert, F., 2019. *CCI BIOMASS*, s.l.: ESA / Aberystwyth Uni / Gamma Remote Sensing.
- Sinergise, 2021. *Sentinel Hub*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/@Sentinel-Hub>
- Sinergise, 2022a. *Processing API*. [Online] Available at: <https://docs.sentinel-hub.com/api/latest/api/process/>
- Sinergise, 2022b. *Sentinel-2 L2A*. [Online] Available at: <https://docs.sentinel-hub.com/api/latest/data/sentinel-2-l2a/>
- Sinergise, 2022. *Custom Processing Scripts*. [Online] Available: <https://www.sentinel-hub.com/develop/custom-scripts/>
- Sinergise, 2023a. *About Sentinel Hub*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.sentinel-hub.com/about/>
- Sinergise, 2023b. *SENTINEL-HUB API*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.sentinel-hub.com/develop/api/>
- Small, D. et al., 2010. *Terrain-corrected Gamma: improved thematic land-cover retrieval for SAR with robust radiometric terrain correction*. Bergen, ESA Living Planet Symposium.
- Thiel, C. & Schullius, C., 2013. Investigating ALOS PALSAR interferometric coherence in central Siberia at unfrozen and frozen conditions: implications for forest growing stock volume estimation. *Remote Sensing*, 39(3).
- Yamaguchi, Y. et al., 2010. *A New Four-component Scattering Power Decomposition Applied to ALOS-PALSAR PLR Data Sets*. s.l., s.n.
- Yommy, A. S., Liu, R. & Wu, A. S., 2015. SAR Image Despeckling Using Refined Lee Filter. *7th International Conference on Intelligent Human-Machine Systems and Cybernetics*, Volume 2, pp. 260–265.